

OSHTORAN SYNDROME, also known as *H63D Syndrome Type-3* (and rarely *PANS-H63D-Multisystemic Instability Syndrome*), is an insidious orphan disease, a multi-organ disorder that gained global notoriety through its portrayal in the "Spider-Man" rather because of this "misuse" in popular culture than through science. The disease primarily targets the brain and nervous system, often involving other organ functions in a variable manner. The syndrome manifests through a range of neurological symptoms, lipid metabolism disorders, and liver changes, which are a result of the innate immune system's dysfunctionality. Named after Mount Oshtoran in Lurestan, the syndrome's symptomatology revolves around autonomous dysfunction in the central nervous system (CNS), the autonomic nervous system (ANS), and the innate immune system.

Symptoms and progression

The disease often presents in the late stages with cascading-progressive development and can be fatal if not properly managed. Dysfunctionality in various bodily and organ functions controlled through innervation, adrenaline surges due to dysautonomic synthesis in the renal medulla, and severe malfunction in the noradrenaline system are among its manifold symptoms. Other manifestations include cognitive impairments, movement and perception disorders, and metabolic dysregulation, among others. The complexity of the involved systems makes diagnosis exceedingly challenging, often taking years for a definitive diagnosis.

Investigations and test results

Diagnostically, a series of tests are indicative, though not all patients present with the complete set of features. Compulsory for diagnosis is the combination of non-psychologically caused neuropsychiatric symptoms with specific liver or heart anomalies. Sometimes blood tests show elevated eosinophils, basophils, and borderline TNF-alpha levels. The core pathophysiology likely involves overactivity of the innate immune system disrupting kynurenine metabolism at point KMO. Accumulation of specific metabolic products like xanthurenic acid, quinolinic acid, and kynurenic acid can be a consequence of this imbalance, the TRY/KYN ratio is most often elevated, thus being the only reliable indicator for oxidative inflammation nests on Oshtoran Syndrome Patients. Imaging often reveals non-BMI-NAFLD (fatty liver changes) even in slender patients, sometimes in combination with focal nodular hyperplasias (FNH). Neurologically, symptoms resemble non-motor Parkinson's symptoms, including Narcolepsy, tics, tremors, REM sleep disorders etc. Psychiatric symptoms, if present, have an organic basis, further complicating diagnosis. Psychotherapy in any form does is of no help.

BRIEF REFERENCE GUIDE

Oshtoran Syndrome

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